

Using the AdS/CFT duality as a guideline, through QIH, the surface area of a black hole (or the event horizon) in Anti-de Sitter space (AdS) can be mapped to a quantum system living on the boundary (Conformal Field Theory, or CFT).

Let's define our representation:

Given the surface area A of the black hole, the maximum number of "qubits" or degrees of freedom N can be represented as: $N = A/(4l_p^2)$

Where l_p is the Planck length.

Each individual light ray converging constructively at the singularity, can still be represented by a state vector, $|\phi_i\rangle$. The collective state of these light rays at the singularity can be given by:

$$|\Phi_{\text{singularity}}\rangle = \sum_{i=1}^N c_i |\phi_i\rangle$$

The Bekenstein bound restricts the number of possible configurations, so if we assume the singularity is a superposition of all possible configurations up to this bound:

$$|\Psi_{\text{singularity}}\rangle = \sum_{j=1}^N a_j |\chi_j\rangle$$

The interference pattern that arises at the singularity, a result of both the light rays and the universe interference pattern configurations, can be described as:

$$|\Theta\rangle = |\Phi_{\text{singularity}}\rangle \otimes |\Psi_{\text{singularity}}\rangle$$

This interference pattern, under the illumination of a converged light ray (akin to a super-entangled beam), gets projected as a hologram. The projection can be modeled by:

$$U_{\text{holography}} |\Theta\rangle = |\Theta_{\text{boundary}}\rangle$$

Incorporating the dynamics of Hawking radiation, this holographic projection evolves over time:

$$e^{-iHt/\hbar} U_{\text{holography}} |\Theta\rangle = |\Theta_{\text{evolved}}\rangle$$

Through QIH, the singularity of a black hole emerges as a finite, yet incredibly intricate, confluence of converging light rays and all possible universe configurations, bounded by the Bekenstein limit. Under the influence of a powerful entangled light ray, the singularity's interference patterns get projected onto a boundary—this projection dynamically evolves due to the effects of Hawking radiation, creating the vast holographic multiverse we might perceive.